

EAC Lidar Guidelines – Baseline Survey Report

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Introduction

This short report is a summary of the responses from a baseline survey conducted online in spring 2022 in advance of the development of new EAC guidelines for the use of lidar in heritage management across Europe. It also gives an update on the progress of the project through delivery of an online seminar in July and development of working groups through August.

The survey questions are provided as an appendix to this document and were designed to establish the status quo for the use of lidar data in 2022, gathering views on the major challenges facing both organisations and individual practitioners. We also asked what formal or informal guidance was being used currently and which topics respondents would like to see covered by any new pan-European Guidance.

The response to the survey was excellent and the results were extremely informative providing an excellent baseline for the development of the EAC lidar guidelines. We extend our thanks to those who gave their time to complete the survey and support the project and to the EAC board for supporting the dissemination of the survey link to partner nations.

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EAC Lidar in Heritage Management survey

The online survey was designed by Rebecca Bennett and Rachel Opitz and hosted as a Google Form. It was live for eight weeks from 1st May to the 30th June 2022 and was promoted through the EAC board, the contacts of the EAC Remote Sensing Working Group and the membership of special interest groups (Aerial Archaeology Research Group, International Society for Archaeological Prospection, Chartered Institute for Archaeologists – Special Interest Group on Remote Sensing).

Respondent Summary

We received 107 responses from 30 countries, including 26 out of 34 EAC member / associate countries.

Austria	Estonia	Ireland	Netherlands	Slovakia
Belgium	Finland	Italy (Including Trento)	Norway	Slovenia
Bulgaria	France	Latvia	Poland	Spain
Croatia	Germany	Lithuania	Portugal	Switzerland
Czechia	Hungary	Luxembourg	Romania	UK ¹
Denmark	Iceland	Macedonia	Russian Federation ²	USA

¹ *England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland are classed as separate EAC countries. We received responses from England Wales and Scotland and also some from organisations working across the UK. We did not receive any responses specifically from organisations or individuals based in Northern Ireland.*

² *The Council of Europe suspended the Russian Federation from its rights of representation in the Committee of Ministers and in the Parliamentary Assembly (25 February 2022) and from 16 March 2022 the Russian Federation is no longer a member of the Council of Europe. As a result, the Board of the European Archaeological Council has agreed that the Russian Federation’s formal membership of EAC should be suspended. As archaeologists working tirelessly to ensure that all members of the Council of Europe are able to join EAC to improve relationships between state parties responsible for archaeological heritage management, the EAC Board regrets this decision keenly. They earnestly hope that matters will improve quickly so the EAC can develop a much-desired partnership with Russian colleagues.*

The highest number of responses were from the UK (43% including disaggregated data for all UK, England, Scotland and Wales), followed by Slovakia, Germany and Spain.

Country	% of responses
UK	19.63%
UK – England	15.89%
UK – Wales	5.61%
Slovakia	4.67%
Germany	4.67%
Spain	3.74%
Bulgaria	2.80%
France	2.80%
Netherlands	2.80%
Ireland	2.80%
UK – Scotland	2.80%
Italy	2.80%
USA	2.80%
Czechia	1.87%
Belgium	1.87%
Romania	1.87%
Estonia	1.87%
Slovenia	1.87%
Austria	1.87%
Norway	1.87%
Portugal	1.87%
Hungary	0.93%
Croatia	0.93%
Poland	0.93%
Macedonia	0.93%
Switzerland	0.93%
Russia	0.93%
Iceland	0.93%
Finland	0.93%
Denmark	0.93%
Latvia	0.93%
Lithuania	0.93%
Luxembourg	0.93%

Respondents could chose to respond on behalf of themselves (47%) or their organisation (53%). We mapped the role of participants into five categories with the majority of responses from Cultural Heritage managers and an even split of researchers and commercial archaeologists.

Role	Count
Cultural Heritage Manager	43
Researcher	26
Commercial Archaeology	23
Early Career Researcher	12
Community Archaeology	3

We asked respondents to share something about their experience working with lidar data and the capacity within their organisations. Around half of the respondents answered this question and the pattern was for small numbers of trained staff, typically 1-3 per organisation have experience of working with lidar. Most frequently these individuals have combined expertise in GIS, geomatics, lidar analysis and interpretation. Around half the respondents assessed themselves as having a good to high level of expertise in working with archaeological lidar and more than half of respondents suggest their expertise and capacity is adequate to the needs of the organisation.

How do you use lidar?

The respondents were asked to categorise how they currently use lidar with the question: **What are the main applications of lidar in your work / your organisation's work?**

The most common use for organisations was **heritage management** while for individuals it was **research**. The lowest use category for all was **community engagement** with less than half of organisations, and only 13% of individuals are using lidar for this purpose.

Additional uses noted by respondents were prospection, targeted field survey, digital preservation, climate change and coastal monitoring, transport infrastructure policy and rights of way / property boundary disputes.

Category	research	heritage management	landscape assessment	planning and development control	community engagement
Organisations (55 responses)	37	43	34	28	20
Individuals (53 responses)	45	33	28	15	13

Figure 1: Table to show the count of respondents for each lidar use category

Figure 2: Graph illustrating % of respondents by sub-sector category

What are the main challenges your organisation faces when using lidar data?

Data Quality and Accessibility: varies within and between countries, poor dissemination of data, re-use of archive data problematic without metadata, cost of purchasing data or acquiring new, refinement of point cloud classification for archaeological purposes

Lack of Standards and Guidance: how to be a knowledgeable client, level the playing field of service provision as clients currently find it hard to compare services, reliability of UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) survey, lack of formal training, lack of clear definition of the limits of the technique and the impact of these on heritage management decisions.

Resourcing and Capacity: including infrastructure issues such as the availability of fast broadband internet connections to facilitate data transfer, handling big data is challenging within and between organisations, challenge to integrate and manage huge numbers of new potential sites, ability to access specialist software (cost of proprietary and IT restrictions for FOSS), too little time for ground observations, upscaling protocols to meet availability of landscape data, capacity to support public engagement with data interpretation.

Skills and Capability: lack of time and trained personnel to undertake systematic analysis, lack of capacity to reprocess older datasets, lack of capacity / interest in the sector nationally, lack of capacity to undertake analytical or integrative work, keeping technical skills of personnel up to data and training more personnel to meet demand, ability to process point cloud data

Recording protocols: how and what to digitise, vector and database choices to help structure the data captures, feature identification and integration with other datasets

Strategic integration: strategic integration of lidar work and outputs at a corporate, regional or national level can be challenging

Public Engagement: concerns regarding public access to data increasing opportunities for nighthawking and increased metal detection activity putting sites at risk, perception of lidar as a deskbased tool inhibits integration into fieldwork programmes,

New Lidar Guidelines

What guidance documents are currently in use?

Of the 107 respondents who answered this question 84% used some form of informal or formal guidance document to assist their work with lidar data. 51% reported that they used more than one source.

- 48% used the Historic England guidance document
- 42% used Kokalj & Hesse
- 25% used resources derived from training sessions or summer schools
- 23% used online resources
- 15% used their organisation’s own internal guidance
- 16% used no guidance documents
- Other resources mentioned included direct access to research papers / literature survey, personal experience, Interpreting Archaeological Topography: 3D Data, Visualisation and Observation (Opitz, Rachel S., and David C. Cowley, editors. 2013) and The Survey Association guidance.

Figure 3: Graph illustrating % of respondents by guidance document

In terms of internal guidance the following organisations were noted as having internal guides and documentation covering the preparation, use and interpretation of lidar data:

RPS PLC, University of Brighton, agentschap Onroerend Erfgoed/ Flemish heritage agency, Austrian Federal Monuments Authority, Institute for the protection of the cultural heritage of Slovenia, Department of Theoretical Geodesy and Geoinformatics Faculty of Civil Engineering, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, The National Trust, Institute of Archaeology CAS, Prague, Historic Environment Scotland, North Northamptonshire Council,

Air Photo Services Ltd, Moesgaard Museum, Keltenwelt am Glauberg, Nottinghamshire
County Council, Monument Board of Slovak Republic, National Institute for Cultural
Heritage Poland.

Typically these internal good practice guides were curated by a specialist in GIS or spatial analytics, and were often tailored versions of the published guidance or training materials. Some organisations also reported that they had standardised their digital workflows for lidar using tools such as ArcGIS and LAsTools.

What would you like to see in the EAC European lidar guidelines?

The following topics were raised as being relevant to the creation of any new European-wide guidelines.

Commissioning Survey: Understanding full waveform and UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) survey platforms (benefits and limitations), project planning guidance, data quality assessment, a minimum standard for data collection covering precision, accuracy, resolution and environmental / survey conditions.

Lidar Data Archives: How to locate data, understanding and accessing metadata, clarity of terminology raw, clear protocols to express the limits of lidar data and interpretation

Processing: open access to processing workflows, focus on reproducibility, tips for visualisation, integration with GIS, use of flowcharts to break processes down into decision points and steps, understanding the impact of resolution by feature form, step by step procedures for using and processing LAS/LAZ files with FOSS tools, varying point cloud classification by landform and use, practical and concise statements regarding the use of multiple and specific visualisations.

Interpretation and Recording: vectorisation standards and examples, how to integrate in to commercial archaeological assessments, correction of common misconceptions, working with multitemporal data, cartographic standards for display of visualisations and derived data, catalogue of feature examples, how to use lidar data holistically, definitions / consideration of the accuracy of interpretations, the cognitive value of lidar as a technique and how to evaluate archaeological entities and landscapes.

Automated Feature Detection: review of status quo, consideration given to what can be done to future-proof guidelines for integrating AI detections

Metadata / Paradata: structure, storage and publication of metadata and paradata

Data Management: formats and storage, software evaluation, long term data management strategies and repositories for short term projects, data exchange, ownership and public interest

Planning, Development Control and Heritage Management: limits of the technology with specific respect to planning and development, best practice for communications with non-specialists, integration with heritage management practices, press for the obligation to integrate lidar into management and assessments wherever it is available

Public and Non-Specialist Engagement: best practice to explain the limitations of lidar to the public and non-specialist colleagues, integration of interpretations derives from citizen science into heritage management,

Case studies: Examples of different practices across Europe and how they are affected by the different levels of data availability, example feature types, geoarchaeological and landform analysis, demonstrating best

practice across a range of landuse / environment / archaeological feature types, climate change, consideration of different scales of work from site through to landscape.

Additional suggestions included the creation of a permanent steering group to oversee and update the document at regular intervals and to support the integration of emerging technology or methods. To this end confederation should be given to the production of the guidelines as a digital resource that is regularly updated. It was also emphasised that the users of the guidelines will be very varied from novices to very experience lidar practitioners and the language used and supporting resources (glossary, references etc) should reflect this. Consideration should be given to making the language, structure and presentation of the guidelines as accessible as possible for neurodivergent and dyslexic users.

Do you wish to be involved in the EAC lidar guidelines working group?

Of the 107 respondents, 66 (61%) indicated that they would like to be involved in the working group going forward.

Project Progress Update

Introductory Seminar 13th July 2022 and formation of Working Groups

On the 13th July we hosted an introductory seminar online to present the results of the survey to participants and facilitate open discussion about the format and content of the EAC lidar guidelines. The seminar was attended by 46 individuals from across Europe and there was excellent engagement in the discussions. The input of the participants was vital to formulating the content, structure and format of the guidelines but also highlighting the need for professional networks and upskilling / training opportunities within the sector.

Following on from the survey and seminar, 34 people have indicated their intention to collaborate in the working groups for the guidelines. Through July and August we have been collecting comments on a [draft structure for the guidelines](#) (see Appendix 2) and will progress to formalising working groups based on this structure through autumn.

Concluding Remarks

The excellent engagement with the survey demonstrates the interest in and need for additional sector-wide guidance in the use of lidar. With such a range and depth of response, covering almost all countries and a great cross-section of professional working in different specialisms, we can consider the responses collated to be a representative baseline of the use of lidar across Europe.

Likewise the attendance and engagement with the initial seminar and subsequent formulation of working groups has also been very positive. The strength of response has also demonstrated the need for a network of professionals and ongoing opportunities for continuing professional development in the sector. We plan to not only work with the 30+ individuals who wish to actively contribute to the guidance document but to continue to communicate with the wider network in order to secure the long-term relevance and impact of the EAC Lidar Guidelines project.

Appendix 1 – Lidar In Heritage Management Survey Questions

The following personal data were collected for each survey participant:

Full Name, Email, Organisation, Role, Country

Participants were then asked the following questions. They could answer both on behalf of an organisation or themselves (or both).

Are you answering on behalf of your organisation or as an individual?

Organisational

What are the main applications of lidar in your organisation's work? Select all that apply.

What expertise and capacity do you have within your organisation?

What are the main challenges your organisation faces when using lidar data?

What guidance documents does your organisation currently use?

If your answer above indicated that you use guidance internal to your organisation, can you supply some more details of what this covers and who curates it?

Individual

What are the main applications of lidar in your work? Select all that apply.

What expertise and capacity do you have?

What are the main challenges you face when using lidar data?

What guidance documents do you currently use?

If your answer above indicated that you use guidance internal to your organisation, can you supply some more details of what this covers and who curates it?

What would you like to see in European lidar guidelines?

Do you wish to be involved in the EAC lidar guidelines working group?

Do you wish to nominate a colleague to take part in the working group? Please note you must have their permission to add their name here!

Appendix 2 – EAC Lidar Guidelines Draft Structure

Sections	Subsections
Part 1: Acquiring Airborne Laser Scanning Survey Approx Word Count: 7500	Introduction What is ALS Justification for survey <i>ALS instrument types and platforms</i> Assessing existing lidar data <i>Considering the needs of other stakeholders</i> Commissioning new survey <i>Resource checklist</i>
Part 2: Data processing and Interpretation Approx Word Count: 9000	<i>Data quality checks</i> Data treatment (processing - classification, terrain modelling, visualisation) Expert-led visual interpretation Integrating Automation Crowdsourcing and Citizen Science Integration with Fieldwork Competence of Personnel <i>Workflow documentation template</i>
Part 3: Reporting and Archiving Approx Word Count: 10500	Best practice for desk based reporting Data presentation Metadata and paradata Data archiving Standards for data interchange Dissemination Public outreach <i>Outputs checklist</i>
Part 4: Applications and Management Considerations Approx Word Count: 9000	Lidar for feature discovery and change detection Lidar for Geoarchaeological Applications Integrating Lidar with Historic Environment Records Lidar in the context of planning and development control Lidar for landscape management Challenges and Potential of multidisciplinary integration for heritage management <i>Value added and limitations summary</i>
Part 5: Considerations for specific environments Approx Word Count: 7000 + national case studies (if pursued)	Agricultural, Coastal, Forest, Pasture, Urban, Uplands, Wetland National case studies / challenge case studies
Part 6: Thesauri of Terms Part 7: References Part 8: Appendices	Related Standards, Codes and Guidance List of Contributors List of Consultees